

Note on Contributors

(In order of Appearance)

Saikat Pradhan serves as a Junior Research Fellow in English Studies at the University of North Bengal. His scholarly interests span the intersections of literature and psychoanalysis, memory and trauma studies, cultural geography, and urban architecture. Pradhan's work also explores the cinematic portrayal of queer identities.

Edcel Javier Cintron-Gonzalez is a proud Puerto Rican, and scholar who is pursuing a Ph.D. in English Studies with a focus in Children and Young Adult Literature. When he is not working on academic things, he enjoys cooking, playing video games and writing about them in the website *Gamers with Glasses* and writing his monthly children's literature review in Spanish for the *Palabreadores Newsletter*. Edcel is the author of *Irma, Maria, Fiona, and Me* published in May 2023 by PRESS 254/Spoonfuls and is a featured speaker for *TEDxNormal* 2024 where he talked about the importance of hurricane narratives.

Maitrayee Mukherjee is a project assistant for the Endangered Archives Program, a collaboration between the Institute of Language Studies and Research (ILSR), Kolkata, and the British Library. She holds a postgraduate degree in Comparative Literature from Jadavpur University and aspires to an academic career. Mukherjee's research interests encompass postcolonial literature, feminist writings, digital humanities, cultural studies, and South Asian studies.

Matias Corbett Garcez is a professor of Anglophone literature at the Federal University of Santa Catarina, Brazil, also contributing to the Graduate Program in English: Linguistic and Literary Studies. His master's thesis explored Beat poetry's influence on Brazil's Tropicália movement, while his doctoral work examined Gil Scott-Heron's afrofuturistic sonic fiction. Garcez has published on audio culture poetics and resistance movements. His current research focuses on performance as a narrative and educational tool. His academic interests include cultural studies, performance studies, literary studies, and narratology. Garcez is also an author, having published a book of short stories and a poetry collection.

Harshita Manchanda is an Editor at QBS Learning. She holds a Master's and Bachelor's degree in English Literature from Indraprastha College for Women and Lakshmi Bai College, Delhi University, respectively. Manchanda's work combines

creative insight with academic rigour, focusing on crafting content that resonates emotionally and intellectually in contemporary contexts. Her research interests include Indian Diaspora, Post-Colonial, and Feminist Writings, reflecting her commitment to exploring diverse literary perspectives.

Crystal Calhoun is an instructor of English at West Georgia Technical College. She holds three degrees, including a Master's from the University of West Georgia, and graduated cum laude. Currently preparing for doctoral studies, Calhoun's academic focus lies primarily in American literature and sensation fiction. She has presented at several professional conferences, including the College English Association, National Council of Teachers in English, and the Conference of English Education. Calhoun's passion for learning extends to her leisure activities, where she writes analytical essays on recent books and films.

Rusha Chowdhury (she/they/he) is a person who stutters (PWS) pursuing a postgraduate degree in English Literature at Jadavpur University. Their research interests include disability studies, with a focus on dysfluency, as well as feminism, queer studies, and ecocriticism. Chowdhury has presented papers at various institutions, including Jadavpur University, Delhi University, and the University of Liverpool. Their work has been published in journals from Lady Shree Ram College and Jadavpur University's Centre for Disability Studies. Alongside academic pursuits, Chowdhury is involved in stuttering pride activism through The Indian Stammering Association and social media advocacy.

Martina Lamberti, a secondary school English Literature teacher, holds degrees from the University of Calabria: a Bachelor's in Modern Languages and Cultures (2016) and a Master's with honours in Foreign Modern Languages and Literatures (2018). Her master's thesis examined the Anglo-Saxon *Vercelli Book*. In 2022, she completed a second-level Master's in English from the University Suor Orsola Benincasa. Lamberti specializes in Germanic Middle Ages and Anglo-Saxon Literature, focusing on religious beliefs, magic, and medical practices. She has published articles on various Anglo-Saxon topics, including the Old English poem *Elene*, the *Merseburg Charms*, medical manuscripts, the goddess Eostre, and the *Vercelli Book*.

Indira Jadav is a Research Scholar in the Department of English at The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda. She is pursuing her Ph.D. on "Revisiting Nationalism in Select Letters of Indian Thinkers." Her research interests include Cultural Studies, Indian English Literature, and Communication Skills, with a focus on the historical and cultural dimensions of Indian nationalism. Jadav's work particularly emphasizes influential figures like Raja

Rammohan Roy and Mahatma Gandhi. She has presented three papers at national and international seminars and conferences, contributing to academic discussions in her field of study.

Audrey T. Heffers, also writing as Audrey T. Carroll, is the author of *What Blooms in the Dark* (ELJ Editions, 2024), *In My Next Queer Life, I Want to Be* (kith books, 2023), and *Parts of Speech: A Disabled Dictionary* (Alien Buddha, 2023). Her scholarly interests encompass Creative Writing Studies, Queer Studies, Disability Studies, and inclusive pedagogy. Heffers serves as Chair of Publications for the Creative Writing Studies Organization and as Diversity & Inclusion Editor for the *Journal of Creative Writing Studies*. She is also the founder and Editor-in-Chief of *Genrepunk Magazine*. She can be found on *Twitter* and *Instagram* @AudreyTCarroll. For more information, visit her website at <https://audreytcarrollwrites.weebly.com/>.

Sayan Chattopadhyay is a Doctoral Researcher and Faculty of English at Adamas University, India, and serves as an Editor for the *Journal of Science Fiction*, affiliated with the Museum of Science Fiction in Washington DC. His research spans Dystopia and Utopia, Post-animalism, and Political Science Fiction. Sayan has presented at numerous international conferences, including PopCRN 2023, SASA Conference 2023, and the IASFS Conference 2023. His scholarly works are indexed in Elsevier, MLA, EBSCO, and Index Copernicus databases.

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